

INTERACTIVE LEARNING METHODS AS A MEANS OF DEVELOPING KEY COMPETENCIES

Kamolov Dilshod Husniddin ugli

The English teacher of the secondary school № 5,
Bukhara region, Shofirkon district, Uzbekistan
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13902732>

Annotation: Interactive teaching methods as a means of forming key competencies. This article analyzes the teaching methods and theoretical foundations of interactive teaching methods.

Key words: interactive; personalized, self-testing, positive interdependence, personal responsibility, facilitating interaction.

Аннотация. Ушбу мақолада интерактив таълим усулларининг ўқитиш усуллари ва назарий асослари таҳлил қилинади.

Калит сўзлар: интерактив, индивидуализацияланган, ўз-ўзини синаб кўриш, ижобий ўзаро боғлиқлик, шахсий ўзаро ҳамкорликни қўллаб-қувватловчи жавобгарлик.

Аннотация. В этой статье анализируются методы обучения и теоретические основы интерактивных методов обучения.

Ключевые слова: интерактивные; индивидуализированные, самотестирование, позитивная взаимозависимость, личная ответственность, содействующее взаимодействие.

The competence-based approach to organizing the educational process necessitates a shift in how teachers approach the learning experience: its structure, modes of activity, and principles of interaction among participants. This entails prioritizing dialogic methods of communication, collaborative knowledge-building, and various creative endeavors in the teacher's work. These objectives are achieved through the implementation of interactive teaching strategies.

The benefits of interactive teaching methods include:

1. Stimulating students' interest in the subject matter.
2. Encouraging active participation from all students in the learning process.
3. Addressing the emotional needs of each individual student.
4. Enhancing the effective absorption of educational content.
5. Having a multifaceted effect on students' development.
6. Providing feedback through audience response.
7. Shaping students' views and attitudes.

8. Developing life skills.

9. Contributing to behavioral change.

Currently, educators categorize all teaching methods as follows: teacher-centered, interactive, individualized, and experience-based.

Methods that focus on the teacher include programmed tasks, which are typically presented in a format and aim to develop specific skills, such as the correct use of medical terminology or the solution of typical mathematical problems.

An educational and methodological module is a stand alone component of an educational program or training course that is based on the completion of specially designed tasks. This ensures the management of students when performing various activities with a variety of learning materials.

Self-assessment tests - These are given to students to help them identify which skills and abilities need improvement.

Computer-assisted instruction (CAI) - All educational materials are transformed into an electronic format and stored on a computer. This method may incorporate all aspects of the previous two methods.

Experience-based learning methods include:

Field experiments - working directly "in the field", with an experienced mentor. The instructor can use lectures or demonstrations to prepare students.

Clinical exercises are conducted at a clinical setting under the guidance and supervision of an instructor.

Laboratory activities are carried out in a laboratory under the supervision of an educator.

Role-playing games - participants are given a scenario and characteristics of characters involved. Students choose a role and attempt to act as that character in a given scenario.

Simulation exercises are simulations of real-life scenarios taken from practice in a simplified format.

Currently, there has been a growing discussion regarding the need for the implementation of interactive teaching methods in education. These methods involve co-participation, with both students and teachers being active participants in the learning process. The role of the teacher often shifts from that of sole knowledge provider to that of a facilitator, organizer, and creator of an environment conducive to student initiative.

Interactive teaching in the classroom is founded on five key principles: positive interdependence among students, personal responsibility for learning,

supportive interaction among all participants, teamwork, and the development of group skills. This approach eliminates the dominance of any one individual or opinion within the learning environment.

Interactive teaching methods allow for the activation of students' educational potential, the introduction of competition elements into the learning process, and the use of all available resources.

The implementation of interactive teaching techniques facilitates communication between teachers and students, as well as among students themselves, both in the classroom and outside of it, including remote classrooms and other locations. The choice of which interactive method to use and how to implement it depends on the learning objectives.

References:

1. Н.Н.Азизходжаева. Педагогические технологии в подготовке учителя. -Т., 2000.
2. Аванесов Р.И, Сидоров В.Н. Очерк грамматики русского литературного языка. 4.1. М., 2005. - 122 с

